

How learning about behavioural biases can improve financial literacy?

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Summary

1. This policy brief presents evidence from a randomized controlled trial showing that behavioural-based financial education significantly improves financial literacy and reduces myopic bias among secondary school students.
2. Myopia—an overemphasis on short-term gains at the expense of long-term benefits—undermines financial decisions like saving, investing, and retirement planning, making it a key barrier to effective financial literacy.
3. Behavioural-based financial education significantly improves financial literacy (up to 0.67 standard deviations) and reduces myopic bias (up to 0.39 sd).
4. Traditional financial education remains effective for improving financial knowledge but has limited impact on mitigating behavioural biases, especially considering.
5. Policy should prioritize interactive, behavioural-integrated courses focused on practical decision-making, especially for older secondary education students.

1. Introduction

Financial illiteracy is highly linked with poor financial decisions, leading to debt, financial instability, and vulnerability to exploitation (Lusardi, 2019). While traditional financial education improves knowledge, its long-term impact is limited, partly due to overlooked behavioural biases like myopia (Fernandes et al., 2014). Myopic bias—characterized by short-term preferences, risk underestimation, and narrow focus—hinders retirement

planning, savings, and investment decisions (Benartzi & Thaler, 1995).

This policy brief summarises a study by Pitthan & De Witte (2025) that explores a new way to improve financial literacy: behavioural-based financial education. Instead of focusing solely on financial facts, this approach helps students understand and overcome cognitive pitfalls like myopia. The study evaluates a randomised controlled trial conducted among 814 secondary school students in Belgium. It compares the effects of traditional financial education with an

intervention that combines financial topics and behavioural insights—specifically about risk underestimation and short-term preferences.

2. Theory and Methods

Financial illiteracy and behavioural biases are key contributors to suboptimal financial choices. While traditional education targets knowledge acquisition, it may fall short in shaping habits or real-world decisions. This study proposed and tested a novel behavioural-based financial education model, hypothesizing that courses integrating awareness of cognitive biases—especially myopia—would enhance financial literacy both directly and via reduced bias. In Figure 1 we show the hypothesis that behavioural-based financial education could have both a direct and an indirect effect to improve financial literacy mediated by better awareness of behavioural biases, a similar approach from Pitthan & De Witte (2024).

Figure 1: Causal diagram of financial education mechanisms.

We test the new approach to financial education through a large-scale randomized controlled trial (RCT), widely regarded as the gold standard for evaluating policy interventions. The RCT involved 814 students aged 14 to 18 from secondary schools in Flanders, Belgium. These students were randomly assigned to one of four groups to ensure that any differences observed could be attributed to the educational content they received.

The control group received no financial education. One group received a standard course covering basic financial concepts such as savings, insurance, and investment. Two additional groups received the same financial content but with extra materials designed to raise awareness about myopic bias. One version focused on the underestimation of risk, while the other added a component on short-term preferences.

All educational materials were delivered through a digital game-based platform called “Life Path”, simulating real-life financial decisions. Students completed a pre-test before the course and a post-test after it, measuring both financial literacy and the presence of myopic bias.

By comparing outcomes across groups, the study assesses both the direct effect of financial education and whether improved awareness of cognitive biases helps explain gains in financial literacy.

3. Results

All treatment groups improved in financial literacy, but the largest gains (up to 0.67 standard deviations) were seen in the group receiving the full behavioural-based curriculum (risk underestimation + short-term preference). Students also showed reduced myopia (up to 0.39 standard deviations) after completing the behavioural-based courses.

The analysis showed that the improvements in students’ financial literacy were not only a direct result of the education they received, but were also indirectly driven by their increased awareness of the myopic bias. This process—known as mediation analysis—helps to identify whether one factor (in this case,

awareness of myopia) acts as a bridge between an educational intervention and its outcomes. The results confirmed that students who became more aware of how short-term thinking and risk underestimation affect decisions were also those who improved the most in financial literacy. In contrast, students who received only traditional financial education improved in knowledge but showed little change in myopia awareness—and no clear indirect effect on financial literacy through this channel. This highlights the added value of addressing behavioural biases in financial education. Figure 2 illustrates these relationships.

Figure 2: Average causal mediated effect using financial literacy as outcome and myopia as mediator.

Older students benefited the most, as did students with the lowest initial financial literacy. Even individuals with low initial myopia scores improved—suggesting debiasing techniques can benefit a broad audience.

4. Policy Implications

This study provides evidence that financial education can be significantly improved by incorporating behavioural insights. Unlike

traditional approaches that focus mainly on knowledge transfer, behavioural-based financial education addresses the root causes of poor decision-making—such as short-term thinking and risk underestimation. These findings carry several implications for policy at both the national and European levels.

First, national governments and education ministries should integrate behavioural content into financial literacy curricula, particularly in secondary education. Teaching students how behavioural biases influence financial decisions can improve both their knowledge and their ability to apply it in real-life situations. Programs should include practical examples and interactive content, such as digital simulations, to support experiential learning and enhance engagement.

Second, at the European level, initiatives such as the EU Capital Markets Union and consumer financial protection strategies should explicitly support the development of behavioural-based financial education materials. The EU could also promote minimum standards or a shared framework that includes behavioural elements in financial education across Member States, facilitating knowledge exchange and scalability.

Third, this study highlights the value of rigorous evaluation through Randomised Controlled Trials (RCTs). Policymakers should encourage the use of RCTs to test new educational approaches before rolling them out at scale.

Finally, this evidence underscores the need for tailored financial education. Students with initially lower levels of financial literacy benefited the most, suggesting that policies should ensure access to enhanced financial

education for vulnerable groups. Behavioural-based programs can serve as a cost-effective, scalable solution that not only informs students but also equips them to make better decisions, contributing to broader financial stability and social resilience.

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What is EFFEct ?

EFFEct is an impact-driven research project aiming to enhance the quality of education in the EU by providing evidence-based policy recommendations and conducting rigorous research on the education policies of individual EU member states.

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Further Information:

Pitthan, Francisco, and Kristof De Witte. "How learning about behavioural biases can improve financial literacy?." *International Review of Economics & Finance* 99 (2025): 103989.

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